

Open Peer Reviewers in Africa

TRAINER GUIDE

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WHAT IS IT AND WHO IS IT FOR

This **Trainer Guide** is meant to help researchers and professionals who want to be Trainers for the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop series. In order to be a Trainer, we recommend that you have attended the workshop yourself as a cohort trainee.

Our goal is to establish a Trainer-of-Trainers (ToT) model in which workshop participants are encouraged and empowered to mobilize, recruit and train colleagues in their respective scholarly communities.

This guide is NOT meant to be prescriptive about how anyone should conduct their training. We encourage you to consider the content as suggestions for your own training and feel free to adapt it to your needs and circumstances.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

We hope that the content of this guide will help you:

- Adopt and adapt some of the training, facilitating, and assessing theories and practices presented below to your own Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop;
- Access practical tips on how to organize and facilitate your own workshop;
- Find resources to learn more and put the learnings into practice.

CONTENT OVERVIEW

The trainer guide is meant to provide you, the trainer, with information and frameworks on how to conduct reflective and inclusive training in your own version of the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop series.

Much of the content presented below touches on training approaches that embrace the principles of authentic learning experiences, participatory pedagogy and reflective learning, where trainees are encouraged to take ownership of their own learning.

This trainer guide is divided into four sections:

SECTION 1. TRAINING PEDAGOGY: FRAMEWORKS AND APPROACHES

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- Designing Learning Activities
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ABOUT OPEN PEER REVIEWERS IN AFRICA

CONTACT INFORMATION AND FEEDBACK

SECTION 1. TRAINING PEDAGOGY: FRAMEWORKS AND APPROACHES

Moving from a “Teacher-centered” to a “Learner-centered” approach

In designing the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa peer review training we strived to implement a “learner-centered” pedagogical approach as opposed to a “teacher-centered” one. But what do we mean by that?

Teacher-centered approaches tilt the power balance towards the direction of the trainer who presents themselves as the sole source of knowledge, and place the trainees in a position of passive learning.

Learner-centered approaches value and center trainees’ knowledge alongside that of the trainer, promoting a learning process that is collaborative, participatory, and based on mutual exchange of opinions and knowledge. In this sense, the figure of the trainer is more the one of a facilitator, a person who enables participation of all trainees, helps move the conversation forward, and ensures a safe space for debate and discussion.

In this role, the trainer designs the workshop materials and activities with the goal of engaging participants in debate-style learning, sharing experiences and opinions that can help them and the group reflect on what’s presented and provide their own perspectives. In the next section, we will present some theories and practical tips on how to implement a learner-centered approach.

How to implement a learner-centered approach

We will cover two key aspects of learner-centered design: “Backward Design” and “Taxonomy of Significant Learning.”

Backward Design

In talking about “Backward Design,” we draw on the ideas presented by Grant Wiggins and Jay McTighe.¹ They are credited for proposing that one begins any training design with the outcomes in mind. This means the trainer should determine what competencies, skills,

¹ Wiggins, G., & McTighe, J. (2005). *Understanding by Design*.

attitude, feelings, and habits they wish the trainees to have as a result of participating in the training.

In designing the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop with “backward design” in mind, we first identified the **goals of the training**:

- To build capacity and enthusiasm for scholarly open review of preprints among African researchers;
- To offer opportunities to actively participate in peer review and gain recognition through community engagement;
- To help decolonize the academic publishing process by creating equitable opportunities for African researchers to engage, lead, and teach others.

Subsequently, we tried to establish the **learning objectives**, things or actions we envisioned/hoped the trainee would know or be able to do as a consequence of participating in the workshop:

- Give clear, constructive, and actionable feedback;
- Identify how systems of oppression manifest in the peer review process;
- Identify, reflect on, and address biases in peer review;
- Write a manuscript review for a journal or self-organized to a preprint;
- Access opportunities to participate in the open peer review of preprints and build a public profile as a reviewer.

In thinking about what we, trainers, needed to do to ensure trainees would reach these learning objectives by engaging not only with the content but with one another, we intentionally created opportunities for small group discussions, reflection, and experience exchange.

We also determined from the start that it would have been important to have at least one hands-on, practical session in which all participants could put into practice what we had learned together, and, importantly, have a tangible output that they could point to as a testimony to their participation. Module III’s live-streamed preprint journal club, in which all trainees collaboratively review a preprint and then publish the resulting review on PREreview made that possible.

In summary, when starting your own training, you can review these ideas, but also try to adapt the goals and learning objectives to best fit what you think your community of researchers would most need.

In doing so, **we invite you to reflect on the following questions:**

- What are the overall goals of this training?
- What do I wish for the trainees to be able to do/think/feel as a result of participating in this workshop?
- How will trainees know if/what they have learned? Will you provide an opportunity to apply the skills just learned or will they be on their own?
- What do you, the trainer, need to do in order to ensure learning happens?

Another useful framework you can refer to to design your learning objectives is called SMART.² According to this framework, ideal learning objectives present the following characteristics:

- **Specific/Speak** to the trainee directly: The trainer needs to develop the learning objectives by speaking directly to the trainee. For example, By the end of the training YOU will be able to...
- **Measurable:** Learning objectives need to elaborate on how the learning will be assessed, offering a way for the trainer to know if the objectives have been met or not. For example, by the end of the training YOU will be able to demonstrate/analyze etc.

Trainers need to avoid verbs such as “understand”, “know”, and “comprehend” since they are not easily measurable. The trainer should ensure that two verbs are not in one outcome so that it can be more measurable.

- **Applicable:** When the trainer develops the learning objectives, they should elaborate on how the trainee will be able to apply the knowledge and emphasize ways in which the trainee is likely to use the knowledge and skills.
- **Realistic:** The learning objectives should be achievable within the time allocated to the training session/sessions.
- **Time-Focused:** The trainer should provide a clear timeline with expectations around when the trainees are expected to do what.

² The content below is derived from the Pilot Transforming Employability for Social Change in East Africa (TESCEA) course on *Learning Design – Planning for effective learning experiences* conducted by AuthorAID and AFELT in 2021. inasp.info/project/transforming-employability-social-change-east-africa-tescea

Significant Learning Framework

Dee Fink³ is another important scholar whose approaches have informed some of the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop design. He introduced the Taxonomy of Significant Learning which helps the trainer think through how they design courses that ensure rich life-changing learning experiences.

The framework proposed by Dee Fink has 6 components:

1. Knowledge: Open Peer Reviewers in Africa was designed as peer review training for researchers with little or limited experience in peer review. Therefore, the content includes definitions and overviews of most common aspects of peer review. For example, in Module 1, the session begins by defining/describing what peer review, preprint and open peer review are to help trainees ground their understanding on these three foundational concepts of the course. For example:

“Peer review is the evaluation of work by one or more people with similar competencies as the producers of the work. It functions as a form of self-regulation by qualified members of a profession within the relevant field.”

“A preprint is a version of a scholarly or scientific paper that precedes formal peer review and publication in a peer-reviewed scholarly or scientific journal. The preprint may be available, often as a non-typeset version available free, before or after a paper is published in a journal.”

These definitions were also a way for us to set up a way to challenge the *status quo*, and invite participants in an exercise of imagining a better future for peer review, thinking and sharing what aspects of the current peer review system they would keep and what aspect they would let go of.

2. Application: Giving trainees an opportunity to apply what they learned in a facilitated setting is going to help solidify the knowledge and boost their confidence in the newly acquired skills. In Open Peer Reviewers in Africa, Module III is dedicated entirely to hands-on practice of what was learned in the previous two modules. Trainees are guided through the collaborative review of a preprint and have the opportunity to then share the review publicly as a testament to their participation and contribution. See more in the Design Learning Activities section below.

3. Integration: It is also important to provide examples and references so that the trainees can easily identify where the new skills may be transferred to contexts that are

³ Active Learning and Learner Centered Design. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7u_TzuOjPBYY

not directly those presented in the current lessons. For example, in Open Peer Reviewers in Africa, one key goal of the materials is to show trainees how to provide constructive, clear and actionable feedback to a research manuscript. The same principles can also help trainees review grant applications, or even write better manuscripts and research proposals themselves.

Another example drawn from the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop is the discussion around the broad meaning of Systems of Oppression in Module I. After defining them, the facilitators guide trainees through a reflection around how these systems which exist everywhere in society can manifest in the scholarly peer review process. Trainees are then asked to reflect on this question, “What can we do to mitigate systemic oppression in the space we live and work in?” and “What role does equity-oriented solution building play in helping combat systemic oppression?”. In answering these questions, trainees are invited to reflect on how the tools we propose as ways to identify bias in peer review can be adapted to or integrated in other contexts of their personal and professional lives.

4. Human Dimension: Learning is a subjective experience. Even in the context of group learning in which multiple trainees participate in discussions and opinion exchanges like in the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop, ultimately each one of them will internalize the learning as individual human beings. It is important, therefore, to be intentional about providing opportunities for trainees to learn about themselves, their values, who they are and who they want to be in the context of the materials that are taught and with respect to their fellow trainees. The reflection can happen at the individual level, but it is also facilitated as a group discussion in which trainees can, if they wish to, compare and exchange experiences and opinions in a safe and accepting environment.

In the first breakout activity in Module I of the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop, participants are invited to join small-group discussions and think collectively about what a new, ideal process of peer review would look like 30 years from today. For example, what aspects of the current peer review process would they like to keep, and what aspects they would rather see changed or disappear. This exercise is designed to prompt a critical discussion around the *status quo* and stimulate participants’ imagination and problem-solving skills. Participants are also encouraged to identify a note-taker and someone who can then report back the key group discussion points to the main group.

Another example in the workshop is the bias reflection activity in Module II, in which trainees are invited to apply the IDEA-R2 Method to reflect on example biases that a

reviewer may consciously or unconsciously experience when reviewing. Using an example bias that is not necessarily one they have identified in themselves is an exercise to help trainees apply the same framework of thinking to other biases and assumptions they may identify in themselves or others around them.

Finally, in Module II there is also an opportunity for participants to share their lived experiences and emotions around receiving peer review feedback that is more or less clear, constructive, and actionable.

5. Caring: An important part of learning with others in a facilitated setting is that participants can practice how to be kind and respectful of others' opinions. In teaching how to be better peer reviewers, we aim to demonstrate the importance of caring for others, and how to empathize with our peers. Trainees are encouraged to empathize with the researchers whose work is reviewed, so that when they conduct a peer review they can provide feedback that may be critical, but also present it in a way that is constructive, non-judgmental and actionable so that it can be of the most use to the receiver.

6. Learning to Learn: The content of a lesson can never be the ending point for a trainee, and so we must strive to ensure that the learner journey doesn't end with the workshop. It is important therefore for the trainer to provide opportunities and resources for the trainees to practice what they learned, and to undertake further reading should a trainee wish to explore any part of the lesson more in-depth.

For example, in the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop, trainees are offered the opportunity to build their profile as peer reviewers by joining a community of researchers who are committed to sharing feedback to preprints openly (*e.g.*, via PREreview). They are also invited to share their research openly on preprint servers such as AfricArXiv, a dedicated server for research content published by African scholars.

Designing Learning Activities

We previously discussed the importance of hands-on activities in a learner-centered training style. In designing training activities that can help trainees resonate with a message presented by trainers, we want to make sure we provide clear and detailed instructions around what we expect the trainees to do, and not do, during the activity. We also want to emphasize that engagement in the activities is optional, and encourage various participation methods for those with different learning and engagement styles.

For example, participants may quietly contribute by writing on a slide, on post-it notes, or on a shared document before reading their contribution aloud.

In the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop, we decided to include the following hands-on activities:

- **[Module I] Ice-breaker Activity** - designed to “break the ice” and give participants the opportunity to introduce themselves, and think about what they already know about the peer review process by sharing with others their feelings and reactions in response to a series of images.
- **[Module I] New Peer Review Process Imagination Small Group Activity** - designed to engage participants in a critical examination of the current peer review process with the goal of building a new and improved process. For this activity, participants are invited to join a breakout session (if the workshop is conducted virtually with a tool that allows it), and then report the primary discussion points back to the main group. We assigned a slide for each breakout group and instructed them to identify a note taker to facilitate the sharing.
- **[Module I] Systems of Oppression Reflection Small Group Activity** - designed to encourage participants to reflect on the legacy of systemic oppression in the context of peer review and scholarly publishing. This is another breakout activity which participants are encouraged to discuss in small groups before reporting the key reflections back to the main group.
- **[Module II] Bias Reflection Small Group Activity** - designed to practice the application of the IDEA-R2 method to guide a reflection to identify common biases and assumptions that may show up in peer review, and consider what we can do to mitigate them. This is also presented as a breakout activity followed by the large group discussion.
- **[Module II] Constructive Feedback Experience Sharing Activity** - designed to give participants the opportunity to share anecdotes and experiences in giving and receiving feedback in ways that felt more or less constructive, clear and actionable. Sharing experiences can be a very powerful way for participants to make new connections between what they just learned and their previous engagement with the topic. It also helps other participants gain new perspectives that they may not have thought about before.
- **[Module III] Preprint collaborative review** - The entire Module III is dedicated to the collaborative review of a preprint. The trainer here assumes more the role of a facilitator than an actual trainer. The goal is to give participants the opportunity to practice what they have learned in the previous modules and apply the lessons to

a real review. Participants are encouraged to undertake the peer review collaboratively. The challenge for the facilitator is to ensure every participant is enabled to participate fully, choosing whether to verbally deliver their feedback or write it down in the collaborative document.

- **[Module III] Asynchronous preprint review assembly** - The notes taken during Module III's collaborative review contribute to the final preprint review that can then be published on a preprint review service as a testament of the participants' contribution. In our case we used PREreview, which allows for participants to sign the review with their real name or a pseudonym. The review will then become part of the scholarly record (see more about this in the [Resources and Templates](#) section below).

Learning Assessment

It is good practice for the trainer to routinely check with the trainees if the content presented has been clearly delivered, and assess if the learning objectives are actually achieved during and after the training. There are many ways of assessing if learning is happening in the way that was set as the objective. One example is the so-called **formative assessment**,⁴ in which the learner is guided by the trainer in assessing their own learning. This is in contrast to “summative assessments”, which are assessments that are usually offered at the end of training and put the trainer in the position of evaluating the trainees.

In the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop we did not have summative assessments per se—except for an anonymous pre- and post-workshop survey designed to help us trainers collect feedback from participants, and address any issues in future workshops. However, we were able to incorporate formative assessments throughout the training by facilitating activities that were designed to encourage participants to reflect on learnings and to exchange opinions with others. Other examples of formative assessments you may consider adding to your workshop are quizzes, reflective questions for the breakout rooms, and other opportunities for critical and constructive discussion.

⁴ The HEA Legal Education Subject Center provides a useful summary of the [differences between formative and summative assessment](#) as does the [Highland Learning and Teaching Toolkit](#)

SECTION 2. PLANNING YOUR OPEN PEER REVIEWERS IN AFRICA WORKSHOP

This section covers some practical tips that may help guide you when you plan your Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop.

Institutional support

If you are one of the initial trainers recruited to deliver the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa Training, you should have institutional support to carry out this workshop. What do we mean by that? With institutional support we mean that the research institution or organization that you work with would be able to help you with the organization and dissemination of the workshop.

For example, let's say you are a researcher at a research institution. As such, you are able to contact the library and connect with the librarians, faculty members, or administrative staff who may be able to help you find a room from which to host the workshop series. Alternatively, if you decide to hold the workshop virtually (see below), you may be able to receive support in promoting the workshop and recruiting participants by accessing a mailing list that would be disseminated to the whole research community.

If you don't have any kind of institutional support, don't hesitate to ask your mentor for advice (if you have one assigned to you from the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa Team). We may be able to help you find a location or access a virtual platform to hold your workshop.

Participants' recruitment

In recruiting the first cohort of the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa trainees and future trainers, we opened up the call via nominations.⁵ That choice was made because we wanted to make sure we would recruit researchers who had institutional support to help them host the workshop themselves.

⁵ Call for nominations:

elifesciences.org/inside-elifesciences/30ce0914/open-peer-reviewers-in-africa-nominations-are-now-open-to-recruit-future-peer-review-trainers-across-the-continent

To recruit your participants, we recommend you set up a way for your community of researchers to register to the event. We recommend that you open up registration at least 2 weeks in advance of the date you have decided to start the workshop.

For logistical purposes, we recommend that you don't allow more than 20 people to participate in the workshop series. You can decide to keep the registration open until 40 people have registered their interest, and keep the remaining 20 registrants on a waiting list. For transparency, your registration advertisement should explicitly disclose that a cap of 20 registrants is in effect, and that an additional 20 registrants will be added to a waiting list to be contacted in the event of unavailability. To the first 20 people who have registered, you should send an email asking to let you know as soon as possible if they can no longer attend so that you can inform the next registrants on the list. We also advise that you close registration one week before the starting date of the workshop.

Check out our example registration form language in the [Templates](#) section.

Choosing your content

The Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop you likely attended had 3 modules dedicated to peer review training (Module I and II) and practice (Module III), plus an optional module meant to guide you as a trainer (Module IV).

We created some template slides that are available on Zenodo:

- Open Peer Reviewers in Africa - Module I Template Slides - doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7145170](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7145170)
- Template Google Slides for Module II - doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7145213](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7145213)
- Template Google Doc for Module III - doi: [10.5281/zenodo.7145274](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7145274)
- Template Google Doc for Module III Assignment - [10.5281/zenodo.7145288](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7145288)

We are in the process of translating these materials in French and Arabic. Keep an eye on new documents uploaded to [Zenodo's Open Reviewers Community](#).

Each module is meant to last 2 hours and has an amount of content that is calibrated for that time. If you choose to modify the content by adding, changing, or deleting parts as it would better suit your community, be sure to try it out before delivering to your participants to ensure you can deliver it in the allocated amount of time.

Below are some questions you can ask yourself to guide the decision around what to keep, what to change, and what to eliminate:

- Who is my audience? Are they already familiar with the peer review process? Do I need to add more information about the peer review process, what it is, what it is not, etc., so that everyone is on the same page?
- Would this argument/example/discussion point resonate with my audience? For example, when we talk about systems of oppression, we tend to think that those cited in the slides as examples are ubiquitous across human societies. But in reality, some words and concepts may be more or less familiar to any particular group given the cultural context they live in. You can try to bring up examples that would most likely drive the point on given the cultural background of your audience.

Logistics

The first Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop was delivered online. That choice was made based on the fact that our team is based in different locations across the world, and by the fact that we intentionally wanted to recruit participants from different countries across the African continent.

You may also decide to host your workshop online, or you may prefer to host in person - perhaps based at your research institution or organization. Below are some tips and points you may want to consider when deciding the best option for you and your community.

Online Training

Onlining training is generally preferred these days due to the global spread of COVID-19. On the one hand, online training may be considered the best solution because it provides an opportunity for more people to participate without having to travel, and eliminates the risk of exposure to the virus. For people with work or familial obligations that would prevent them from traveling, online participation may be the only option. On the other hand, not everyone may have access to a stable internet connection, so online training may be an obstacle to another subset of trainees.

If you choose to deliver your workshop online, below are some tips/resources for you to consider (also check out these [great resources by the CSCCE team](#)):

- Video Conference Platform: A few options to explore are the following:

- [Zoom](#): 40 mins limit for each call - but contact your mentor as we may be able to give you access to a paid account that would extend that time and increase the number of allowed participants. Zoom was our choice because it allows for breakout sessions and also has live caption services.
- [Google hangouts](#): Free for members with a Google account
- [Skype](#): Free, download the app
- [Jitsi](#): Free, open source web-based calls are possible
- Engagement/brainstorming tools
 - For Module I and II we used Google Slides to present our workshop content AND to engage participants in the hands-on learning activities. For Module III we opted for Google docs to facilitate the collaborative preprint review discussion. You can take the same approach or opt for other engagement tools (examples listed below).
 - [Miro/Mural/Padlet/Jamboard](#) - tools to help brainstorming and collaborative ideation
 - [Etherpad](#) - a tool for collaborative writing similar to Google docs, but without the for-profit company backing. It allows users to click a link, join a doc, and work together synchronously or asynchronously.⁶
- Accessibility
 - In the Templates section, we offer language for your registration form to ensure maximum accessibility for registrants. One of the questions is designed to gauge the accessibility needs of participants, who should indicate if they have any special requests for access to the workshop. Make sure that you check the answers to that question and are ready to accommodate requests for access. Some requests you may not be able to accommodate, and we advise that you consult with your mentors on this matter.
 - Consider offering live captioning services as a way to help participants follow the presentation and increase access to the workshop. Some online tools offer live captioning services (e.g., Zoom paid account) but they are not always very accurate. Check out [this resource](#) for more information about captioning, subtitles, and transcription for online meetings and events.
- Recording or not recording
 - If the video conference platform allows it, we recommend recording the sessions and distributing the recording ONLY amongst participants. This is

⁶ Learn more about Etherpads and its use for collaborative writing:
<https://www.cscce.org/2020/09/25/cscce-community-tools-trial-recap-etherpadvideo>

because you don't want to make participants feel shy or uncomfortable in sharing their experience and opinions knowing that the recording may end up on the internet. Be very clear about the fact that the video recording should not be shared outside the group of participants. You may also choose not to record for that very reason, but that will mean that participants won't have access to the recordings themselves in case they wish to revisit content and discussions.

In-person Training

You may instead decide to offer the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa training in person. Perhaps you have access to a room at your institution or at your workplace and you believe an in-person workshop would better suit your community's needs.

Please note that the materials we made available as templates are geared towards online training. We recommend that you talk to your assigned mentor if you decide to hold the training in person so that you can make the necessary changes to the materials.

If you choose to deliver your workshop in person, below are some tips/resources for you to consider:

- Space
 - We recommend a room in which you can set up tables for groups of participants to sit together so that they can engage in small group discussions (the equivalent of the breakout room sessions on Zoom).
 - Make sure the space is accessible to participants, and that instructions on how to reach it are clear (see more under Accessibility).
 - Make sure there is access to bathrooms.
 - If you need participants to engage online, make sure they have access to a wifi connection.
- Engagement tools
 - Hands-on activities designed primarily for online training can be adapted to suit in person activities. For example, instead of the breakout room, you can ask participants to make small groups of 4 to discuss the prompts of the activity amongst themselves and then report back to the larger group. You can make pens and post-it notes available for participants to take notes during the small group discussions.

- If participants have their own laptops and access to wifi connection, you can possibly keep the hands-on activities online, directing participants to common engagement tools as described in the [Online Training](#) section.
- Accessibility
 - There are several considerations to make in order to host a truly inclusive and accessible event. [This guide](#) includes an accessibility checklist and a sample accommodations form. In a nutshell, please consider:
 - Physical Accessibility: The space has no problems for wheelchair users and people with vision disabilities
 - Sensory Accessibility: The event is safe for people with allergies. There are accommodations for people who are Blind, Deaf, or hard of hearing.
 - Cognitive Accessibility: Give clear information about the event. Provide all material in different formats and plain language. Let people know what to expect in advance.

Participation guidelines and violation enforcement

Participation guidelines or code of conducts are documents that clearly state participation norms, expected and non-tolerated behaviors, ways to report violations, and information about how violations of the code of conduct will be handled.

[The Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop Participation Guidelines](#) are available for you to use or adapt from for your own workshop. However, we recommend that you adapt it to include contact and procedural information about reporting violations to you and/or your host institution or organization.

Mozilla provides some instructions and guidance on how to write your own code of conduct. Check out [this resource](#).

SECTION 3. TEMPLATES

In this section we will provide you with potentially useful template materials that you can use in your own workshop. This includes template workshop advertisements, registration forms, emails to participants, assignments, and template pre- and post-workshop surveys.

Template Workshop Advertisement

Below is some text you can consider adapting to advertise your workshop.

Open Peer Reviewers In Africa - A peer review workshop

WHAT: Open Peer Reviewers in Africa is a FREE workshop offered to scholars who want to learn how to provide constructive, clear, and actionable feedback to research manuscripts, and who are willing to pass their acquired knowledge to others. Via interactive discussions and hands-on activities we will explore how systemic oppression is reflected in peer review and what we can do to ensure our own biases and assumptions do not prevent us from providing the most unbiased and fair feedback to our fellow colleagues.

WHO: This workshop is primarily designed for African-based researchers at early stages of their career with little to no experience in peer review. However, we believe that researchers at all career levels would benefit from attending.

WHEN: [ADD DATES]

REGISTRATION: Register here [insert link to registration form]. Registration will be open until [insert date of registration closure] This workshop will host no more than 20 participants. Registration is first come first serve but we will have a waiting list for the next 20 people who register. We invite people to only register if they are confident they will be able to attend all three sessions. Attendance to all three sessions is required to obtain a certificate of participation.

Template Registration Form

For your registration form you can use Google forms, Zoom directly if that's the tool you are using for the workshop, or any other tool you have access to via your institution. [Here](#) is a list of other available online tools for registration.

Below is some template text you can use in your registration form.

Registration for attending Open Peer Reviewers in Africa - A Peer Review Workshop

Thank you for your interest in participating in the Open Peer Reviewer in Africa Workshop. This is a three-part, free workshop offered by [add your name and the name of your institution if applicable] and developed by a collaboration between AfricArXiv, Eider Africa, eLife, PRereview, and Training Centre in Communication (TCC) Africa (More about this collaboration: <https://elifesciences.org/for-the-press/ce2d4a3e/elife-prereview-and-partners-develop-course-to-involve-more-african-researchers-in-peer-review>).

The workshop will be hosted [insert if online or in person] on the following dates and times:

Module I: [insert date and time]

Module II: [insert date and time]

Module III: [insert date and time]

Please note that this workshop can host a maximum of 20 participants. If you believe you can attend all three sessions, we invite you to register now to secure your seat. Attendance to all three sessions is required to obtain a certificate of participation.

Data collected in this registration form will be used solely for the purpose of registration and communication with the registered participants.

If you have any questions, please contact [insert trainer's email].

Insert email address:

[]

First, Last Name of Participant

[]

Institution/Organization (if applicable)

[]

If you have any access requests, please write them below and we'll try our best to accommodate them

[]

Template Emails

Below we provide template language you can adapt in your own workshop to communicate with the participants. We also offer suggestions for when we think it would be helpful to send those emails, but of course the timing may depend on your own timeline of workshop delivery. You will need to populate the highlighted yellow sections with information relative to your own workshop. The rest of the text will likely also need adaptation—for example, here we imply that the workshop is delivered online, but this will not be the case if you plan to hold the workshop in person.

Email 0/a. Confirmation of registration

Subject: [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa] Thank you for registering!

From: Trainer(s)

To: First 20 people who registered [*Note that depending on the software you use for registration, you may be able to set up an automatic email that is sent upon registration*].

When: Email to be sent to the first 20 people who registered upon registration to inform them that registration has occurred.

Email text:

Hello!

Thank you for registering to participate in the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop! Your seat at the workshop is secured.

We will have a waiting list for people who register after we fill out the 20 available spots at the workshop. Therefore, **we would be very grateful if you could let us know as soon as possible if you can no longer attend the workshop**. Below you will find info about the workshop dates. We ask that you commit to attending all the sessions as attendance is required to obtain the certificate of participation.

We look forward to meeting you and learning together!

Cheers,

[insert name of trainer sending the email]

Module I

WHEN: [insert date and time of the trainings]; find your local time [you can link to [this tool](#) after setting the time and day of the workshop in UTC for example so that it can be used by participants to identify the time in their timezone]

WHERE: Zoom [or the location of the workshop if in person]

Module II

WHEN: [insert date and time of the trainings]; [find your local time](#)

WHERE: Zoom [or the location of the workshop if in person]

Module III

WHEN: Zoom [or the location of the workshop if in person]

Email 0/b. Confirmation of registration and waiting list

Subject: [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa] Thank you for registering! You are in the waiting list

From: Trainer(s)

To: Any registered person after the first 20 people [Note that depending on the software you use for registration, you may be able to set up an automatic email that is sent upon registration. You can change from the email above to this one once you reach 20 registered].

When: Email to be sent to the people who registered after the first 20 upon registration to inform them that registration has occurred but they are on a waiting list.

Email text:

Hello!

Thank you for your interest in participating in the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa workshop! The workshop is currently full but your name has been placed on a waiting list. We will let you know no later than 1 week before the workshop if a spot becomes available for you.

Cheers,

[insert name of trainer sending the email]

Email 1. Welcome and Information about Module I

Subject: [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa] Welcome and Information about Module I

From: Trainer(s)

To: Participants [Note that you can send this email in bulk using bcc so that participants don't see the addresses of other participants as without explicit consent that can be a violation of privacy].

When: Email to be sent by the trainer(s) to the participants who signed up to the workshop series. Ideally this email is sent to participants 1 week prior to Module I.

Email text:

Dear [insert name of participant],

Thank you for registering to participate in the Open Peer Reviewer in Africa. I am really excited to get to know you and learn together during this workshop!

Below you will find information about what to expect and how to join each one of the 3 modules every [insert timeline]. **Please mark your calendar and read the content below carefully.** If you wish for me to send you a calendar invite, please let me know, but be aware that other fellow participants may see your email address in the shared calendar invite.

BEFORE joining Module I, please take a moment to complete our PRE-Workshop Survey: <https://forms.gle/kVN5SVtuOMRyWLzh6>

Module I

WHEN: [insert date and time of the trainings]; find your local time [you can link to [this tool](#) after setting the time and day of the workshop in UTC for example so that it can be used by participants to identify the time in their timezone]

WHERE: Zoom [[insert Zoom link](#)]

WHAT: In this Module we will introduce the peer review process and invite participants to think of ways to improve it. We will also define and talk about the legacy of systems of oppression in the context of scholarly publishing and invite participants to share

their views and reflections. Participation in the discussion will be optional.

Module II

WHEN: [insert date and time of the trainings]; [find your local time](#)

WHERE: Zoom [[insert Zoom link](#)]

WHAT: In this Module we will guide participants on how to go about writing a manuscript review. We will follow guidelines derived from the Open Peer Reviewers Toolkit, and engage participants in conversations aimed at identifying and mitigating biases and assumptions that they may bring to peer review.

Module III

WHEN: [insert date and time of the trainings]; [find your local time](#)

WHERE: Zoom [[insert Zoom link](#)]

WHAT: The goal of this Module is for the participants to collaboratively review a preprint while applying the lessons learned in the previous two modules. The final output of this module will be a published preprint review authored by the participants.

TO DO/KNOW **BEFORE** YOU JOIN

- Please get familiar with our [Participation Guidelines](#) [[Trainer, you are welcome to use our participation guidelines or modify them according to your needs for the training](#)]. We will go over them during Module I and ask you if you have anything to add.
- Please be punctual as we will start no later than 5 minutes after the starting time of the call.
- If you cannot attend one of the modules for any reason, please let us know in advance by contacting [[insert your email address](#)] or replying to this email.

WHAT TO EXPECT

- Each Module will be presented by [[insert number](#)] facilitators.
- The calls will be recorded and the recording will be shared with participants of your cohort only.
- All participants will be invited to group discussions and experience sharing, but engagement will be optional.

I can't wait to meet you. See you all next week!

With best wishes,

[insert name of trainer sending the email]

Email 2. Module I resources and Module II info and assignment

Subject: [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa] Module I resources and Module II info and assignment

From: Trainer(s)

To: Participants [Note that you can send this email in bulk using bcc so that participants don't see the addresses of other participants as without explicit consent that can be a violation of privacy].

When: Email to be sent after Module I and ideally at least 1 week prior to Module II (although the timing may depend on the frequency of the workshop chosen by the trainer).

Email text:

Dear [insert name of participant],

We were thrilled to meet you yesterday! This email contains links to the resources shared in Module I, the link to the video recording, info on how to join Module II and reading assignments.

Module I resources

- Video recording link [[insert link here](#)] - please don't share with anyone outside this group without consent from everyone who participated
- Slides [[insert link to the slides](#)]

Module II info and assignment

- **WHEN:** [[insert day, date and time](#)]- find your local time [[add link](#)]
- **WHERE:** Zoom - [[insert ZOOM link](#)]
- **ASSIGNMENT:** [Before joining next XX](#), please take a moment to read through the Open Reviewers [Bias Reflection Guide](#) and the [Reviewer Guide](#)

Please let me know if you have any questions or concerns.

Looking forward to seeing you again.

Cheers,

[insert name of trainer sending the email]

Email 3. Module II resources and Module III info and assignment

Subject: [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa] Module II resources and Module III info and assignment

From: Trainer(s)

To: Participants [Note that you can send this email in bulk using bcc so that participants don't see the addresses of other participants as without explicit consent that can be a violation of privacy].

When: Email to be sent after Module II and ideally at least 1 week prior to Module III (although the timing may depend on the frequency of the workshop chosen by the trainer).

Email text:

Dear [insert name of participant],

Thank you for joining Module II! This email contains links to the resources shared on Module II, the video/audio recordings, as well as info on how to join Module III and pre-workshop assignments. **Please read the instructions below carefully to make sure you come prepared to Module III.**

Module II resources

- Video recording link [[insert video link](#)] - please don't share with anyone outside this group without consent from everyone who participated
- Slides [[insert link to slides](#)]

Module III info and assignment

- **WHEN:** [[insert day, date and time](#)] - find your local time [[add link](#)]
- **WHERE:** [[insert ZOOM link](#)]
- **WHAT:** Expect to join a collaborative and participatory review session where we will put into practice what we learned in Module I and II. [Here](#) [[insert the link](#)] you can read more about

this type of event, which we call live-streamed preprint journal clubs. **We will be discussing the preprint** titled [insert title of the PReprint]- posted on the preprint server AfricArXiv **[insert a link to the preprint]**.

- **ASSIGNMENT:** In your own time and using the tools we provided during Module II class, we ask that you please complete the following steps *before* you join us for Module III:
 - **(1)** please practice checking biases and assumptions you may hold (STEP 1)
 - **(2)** read the preprint to gain a conceptual understanding (STEP 2)
 - **(3) OPTIONAL:** re-read for evaluation and begin identifying major and minor issues (STEP 3)
 - **(4) OPTIONAL:** begin thinking about how you would suggest the authors addressed the issues (STEP 4). **NOTE:** We will do STEP 3 and 4 together during Module III, but it can be helpful to get some thoughts before you join the discussion.

Please let me know if you have any questions or concerns.

Looking forward to seeing you again!

[Insert name of trainer sending the email]

Email 4. Module III resources and assignment

Subject: [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa] Module III resources and assignment

From: Trainer(s)

To: Participants [Note that you can send this email in bulk using bcc so that participants don't see the addresses of other participants as without explicit consent that can be a violation of privacy].

When: Email to be sent after Module III and ideally at least 1 week prior to the assignment's first deadline.

Email text:

Dear [insert name of participant],

Thanks so much to everyone who participated in Module III. We appreciated all the discussion and engagement! Module III was the

last one of the modules. This next phase will include some asynchronous work aimed at writing up the preprint review and publishing it for the world to see.

This email contains resources shared in Module III and instructions on the assignment.

Module III resources

- Video recording link [[insert link here](#)] - please don't share with anyone outside this group without consent from everyone who participated
- Collaborative notes document [[insert link to the document](#)] - please note the document is configured to comment/suggestion mode now, please don't share with anyone outside this group without consent from everyone who participated

Module III Assignment (short version)

- **By** [[insert date](#)] please complete the following tasks of this assignment:
 - Read the content of this document [[insert link to your Module III assignment document](#)];
 - Add your name to your choice of identity option;
 - Complete Part A of the full PREreview Assignment.
- **By** [[insert date](#)]
 - Complete Part B of the full PREreview Assignment so that we can publish the full PREreview by [[insert date](#)].
 - If you chose identity option 2 or 3, fill out a rapid PREreview of the preprint.

The longer and more detailed version of this assignment can be found here [[insert link to your Module III assignment document](#)].

As always, please don't hesitate to contact me if you have any questions or concerns. I'll be in touch to update everyone on the progress of the full PREreview assembly.

Thank you for your work! Happy preprint reviewing!

[[insert name of trainer sending the email](#)]

Email 5. Preprint review publication and final remarks

Subject: [Open Peer Reviewers in Africa] Preprint review publication and final remarks

From: Trainer(s)

To: Participants [Note that you can send this email in bulk using bcc so that participants don't see the addresses of other participants as without explicit consent that can be a violation of privacy].

When: Email to be sent after Module III Assignment is completed.

Email text:

Dear [insert name of participant],

Thank you for contributing to the writing of the final review report. I am excited to let you know that the review is live and you can access it here [insert link to public review].

I would love it if you could spend 5 minutes to complete this POST-Workshop Survey: <https://forms.gle/uEJHB6kUswugSgiu5> as it would help the Open Peer Reviewers in Africa team improve on the facilitation and organization of these workshops.

After completing your POST-Workshop survey you will find a link to submit your name and email address to be automatically sent a certificate of participation via email.

Thanks again for your participation!

Cheers,

[insert name of trainer sending the email]

Template Module III Assignment

[Here is a link to the Template module III assignment document.](#) Please make a copy before adapting it to your needs. If you do not have access to this document, please contact your assigned mentor or email us at community@elifesciences.org.

Template Pre- and Post-Workshop Surveys

We prepared some pre- and post-workshop surveys that we would like you to share with your participants. If you decide to share these surveys with your participants and would like to access depersonalized information from your participants, please email us at

community@elifesciences.org. The results of these surveys will help us keep track of participation and inform us on how to improve the workshop materials.

- PRE-Workshop Survey: forms.gle/kVN5SVtuQMRyWLzh6
 - To be shared with participants BEFORE they join the first Module.
- POST-Workshop Survey: forms.gle/uEJHB6kUswugSqui5
 - To be shared with participants AFTER completion of the last Module's assignment. The post workshop survey includes a link on completion to a separate form for the participants to submit their name and email address to receive a certificate of participation if they so wish.

SECTION 4. RESOURCES

In this section we list resources we have cited above and many more that we think you may find useful to learn more about any given topic introduced during the workshop, as well as topics which we did not have time to cover during the sessions.

Open Science

Definition on Wikipedia, en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_science

UNESCO Open Science recommendation, unesco.org/en/natural-sciences/open-science

Okune, Angela. (May 29th, 2019). [Decolonizing scholarly data and publishing infrastructures](https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/infrastructures/); blogs.lse.ac.uk

[Open] Peer Review

- **PREreview.** Open Reviewers toolkit
 - [Bias Reflection Guide](#) (assess and mitigate review-related biases)
 - [Reviewer Guide](#) (a step-by-step guide for reviewers)
 - [Review Assessment Rubric](#) (constructively evaluate reviews)
- **ASAPbio Resources for Reviewers.** asapbio.org/pyr-resources
- **How to publish peer reviews.** asapbio.org/how-to-publish-peer-reviews
- **Canada Research Chairs.** [Bias in Peer Review](#) (PDF)
- **Canadian Science Publishing.** [How to write a scientific peer review: a guide for the new reviewer](#)
- **COPE.** Resources collection: Peer Review processes, publicationethics.org/peerreview
- **COPE.** Ethical guidelines for peer reviewers, publicationethics.org/node/19886
- **eLife.** Collection of Peer Review articles, elifesciences.org/collections/0a5cf428/peer-review
- **Enago Academy.** Resources on Peer Review, enago.com/academy/tag/peer-review
- **Enago Academy.** Increasing Diversity and Inclusion in Peer Review,

enago.com/academy/increasing-diversity-and-inclusion-in-peer-review

- **Health Systems Global.** [The peer review process – what happens when you send your manuscript to a journal](#) (A webinar recording that covers the formal process of submitting a manuscript)
- **PLOS.** Peer Review Center, plos.org/resources/for-reviewers
- **Science.** [Peer Review at Science Publications](#)
- **Wiley.** [Step by step guide to reviewing a manuscript](#)

Bezuidenhout, Louise, Havemann, Jo, Kitchen, Stephanie, De Mutiis, Anna, & Owango, Joy. (2020). [African Digital Research Repositories: Mapping the Landscape](#) [preprint]. // [dataset](#)

Fast, Elizabeth, et al. **“Indigenous Knowledges and a Relational Peer Review Process.”** *International Review of Qualitative Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, 2016, pp. 381–84. *JSTOR*, [jstor.org/stable/26372218](https://www.jstor.org/stable/26372218)

Foster, Antoinette, Hindle, Samantha, Murphy, Katrina M., & Saderi, Daniela. (2021). **Open Reviewers Bias Reflection Guide.** Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5484052>

Gregory AT, Denniss AR (2019) **Everything You Need to Know About Peer Review — The Good, The Bad and The Ugly**, DOI: doi.org/10.1016/j.hlc.2019.05.171

Hodgkinson, M., Marincola, E., Aldirdiri, O., & Owango, J. (2020). [State of Open Access in Africa and its Implication on Researchers](#). AfricArXiv. (audio/visual)

Horbach, S.P.J.M., Halffman, W. **Journal Peer Review and Editorial Evaluation: Cautious Innovator or Sleepy Giant?**. *Minerva* **58**, 139–161 (2020). doi.org/10.1007/s11024-019-09388-z

Krummel M, Blish C, Kuhns M, Cadwell K, Oberst A, Goldrath A, Ansel KM, Chi H, O'Connell R, Wherry EJ, Pepper M; Future Immunology Consortium. Universal Principled Review: **A Community-Driven Method to Improve Peer Review.** *Cell*. 2019 Dec 12;179(7):1441-1445. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2019.11.029. PMID: 31835023.

Meadows A (2018). [Eight Ways to Tackle Diversity and Inclusion in Peer Review](#). The Scholarly Kitchen

Okune, Angela. (2019). **Self-Review of Citational Practice.** Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3066861

Owango, J., Obanda, J., Bourguet, D., Marinello, G., Saderi, D., Fornés, A. T., ... Havemann, J. (2020). **Rapid and Open Peer Review** [Webinar]. AfricArXiv. doi.org/10.21428/3b2160cd.dba872ac

Owango, J., Munene, A., Ngugi, J., Havemann, J., Obanda, J., & Saderi, D. (2021). **Best Practices and Innovative Approaches to Peer Review** [incl. workshop recordings]. AfricArXiv. doi.org/10.21428/3b2160cd.c3faf764

Rajagopalan J (2018). [Diverse views on diversity in peer review](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-019-0063-9). Editage Insights

Ross-Hellauer T. **What is open peer review? A systematic review** [version 2; peer review: 4 approved]. *F1000Research* 2017, **6**:588 (doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11369.2)

Ross-Hellauer, T., Görögh, E. **Guidelines for open peer review implementation**. *Res Integr Peer Rev* **4**, 4 (2019). doi.org/10.1186/s41073-019-0063-9

Ross-Hellauer T, Deppe A, Schmidt B (2017) **Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers**. *PLoS ONE* 12(12): e0189311. doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311

Ross-Hellauer, Tony. (2017). OpenAIRE2020 D7.4 - **Novel Models for Open Peer Review**. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1257257

Schmidt B, Ross-Hellauer T, van Edig X and Moylan EC. **Ten considerations for open peer review** [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]. *F1000Research* 2018, **7**:969 (doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.15334.1)

Sebola, M.P., 2018. [Peer review, scholarship and editors of scientific publications: the death of scientific knowledge in Africa](https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-019-0063-9). *KOERS — Bulletin for Christian Scholarship*, 83(1).

Stiller-Reeve M (2018). **How to write a thorough peer review**. doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-06991-0

Superchi, C., González, J.A., Solà, I. *et al.* **Tools used to assess the quality of peer review reports: a methodological systematic review**. *BMC Med Res Methodol* **19**, 48 (2019). doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0688-x

Squazzoni, F., Marusic, A., Seeber, M., Mehmani, B., Willis, M., Hurst, P., ... Grimaldo, F. (2019, November 5). **Data Sharing and Research on Peer Review: A Call to Action**. doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/sr6eg

Tennant, J.P., Ross-Hellauer, T. **The limitations to our understanding of peer review.** Res Integr Peer Rev 5, 6 (2020). // preprint (2019) doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/jq623

Tennant JP, Dugan JM, Graziotin D *et al.* **A multi-disciplinary perspective on emergent and future innovations in peer review** [version 3; peer review: 2 approved]. *F1000Research* 2017, **6**:1151 (doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.12037.3)

Tokalić R. and Marušić A. (2018). [A peer review card exchange game](#), *European Science Editing* 44(3). (A card game covering responsiveness, competence, impartiality, confidentiality, constructive criticism, responsibility)

Mentoring

Akena, Francis Adyanga. 2012. "[Critical Analysis of the Production of Western Knowledge and Its Implications for Indigenous Knowledge and Decolonization](#)." *Journal of Black Studies* Vol. 43 (6): 599–619.

Angela Okune. 25 March 2020, "**Perspectives on Open Access in Africa**", *Research Data Share, Platform for Experimental Collaborative Ethnography*, last modified 10 February 2021, accessed 17 July 2022. researchdatashare.org

Azikiwe, B. N. (1934). "[How shall we educate the African?](#)" *Journal of the Royal African Society*, 33, 143-151.

Carr T, Jaffer S, Smuts J (2009) **Facilitating Online - A course leader's guide**. Centre for Educational Technology, University of Cape Town; open.uct.ac.za/bitstream/handle/11427/7495/FacilitationOnlineWeb.pdf?sequence=3

Friedrich, D. **Effectiveness of peer review as cooperative web-based learning method applied out-of-class in a role playing game: A case study by quasi-experimental approach.** *Smart Learn. Environ.* **6**, 19 (2019). doi.org/10.1186/s40561-019-0102-5

Heleta, S. (2018). [Decolonizing knowledge in South Africa: Dismantling the 'pedagogy of big lies'](#). Ufahamu, A Journal of African Studies.

Mbembe, Achille. 2015. "[Decolonizing Knowledge and the Question of the Archive](#)." *Africa Is A Country* eBook

Munene, A. (2019). **Developing research talent capacities in Africa: Why we must cherish research.** *AuthorAID News*, authoraid.info/en/news/details/1349/

Mentoring Programs

- PREreview Open Reviewers workshop and program (2020), content.prereview.org/openreviewers
 - PREreview Open Reviewers: Reflections on the Pilot Program, content.prereview.org/prereview-open-reviewers-reflections-on-the-pilot-program/
- Mozilla Open Leaders, foundation.mozilla.org/en/initiatives/mozilla-open-leaders/
- Open HardwareMakers, openhardware.space

Event planning and facilitation

- Anti-oppression resource and training alliance, AORTA group, aorta.coop
- Association of Faculty Enrichment in Learning and Teaching in Kenya, afelt.org
- Autistic Advocacy (2019). [Holding Inclusive Events: A Guide to Accessible Event Planning](#). (PDF)
- University College London, UK, [Learning Designer](#). *A visually structured approach to learning design*

Pratt, Katie, Santistevan, Camille, Woodley, Lou, Butland, Stefanie, & Gould van Praag, Cass. (2020). DEI Tip Sheet: **Captioning, subtitles, and transcription for online meetings and events**. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4268671

Pratt, Katie, & Woodley, Lou. (2021). CSCCE Tech Tip Sheet - **Zoom bombing: How to deal with bad actors during Zoom events**. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4645429

Woodley, Lou, Pratt, Katie, & East, Jenny. (2021). **A guide to using virtual events to facilitate community building: Making a PACT for more engaging virtual meetings and events**. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4987666

Woodley, Lou, & Pratt, Katie. (2021). **A guide to using virtual events to facilitate community building: Selecting and testing online tools**. Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4521211

Woodley, Louise, Pratt, Catherine, Ainsworth, Rachael, Amsen, Eva, Bakker, Arne, Butland, Stefanie, O'Donnell, Stephanie, Penfold, Naomi, Pope, Allen, Quigley, Tom, & Tsang, Emmy. (2020). **A guide to using virtual events to facilitate community building: Event formats.** Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934385

Woodley, Lou, Pratt, Katie, Ainsworth, Rachael, Bakker, Arne, Arielle Bennett-Lovell, Bertipaglia, Chiara, Butland, Stefanie, Guay, Samuel, Karvovskaya, Lena, Lescak, Emily, Meier, Ouida, McLean, Erin, Santistevan, Camille, Timm, Kristin, & Vasko, Stephanie E. (2020). **A guide to using virtual events to facilitate community building: Curated resources.** Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4270106

Pedagogy and training materials

AuthorAID. [Training of Trainers Toolkit](#)

Chambers R. (2002). [Participatory workshops: A Sourcebook of 21 Sets of Ideas and Activities](#)

Civil Service Training Centre, Ghana. Training of Trainers Course for Sierra Leone and Liberia: [Effective Training Management and Training Delivery Techniques](#)

Columbia University in the city of New York, USA. [Adapting Your Face-to-Face Course to a Fully Online Course: A Guide](#)

Dhawan, S. (2020). [Online Learning: A Panacea in the Time of COVID-19 Crisis](#). Journal of Educational Technology Systems, 49, 1

Emerge Africa. [Facilitating Online Course Leaders Guide](#) (PDF, 114 pages)

Jisc, UK (2014). [Planning a participatory workshop](#)

Naicker, Visvanathan & Bayat, Abdullah (2016). [Towards a Learner-centred Approach: Interactive Online Peer Assessment](#). South African Journal of Higher Education. 26. 10.20853/26-5-200.

Nakweya G (2021). [Generosity and collegiality as institutions embrace blended learning](#). University World News - Africa Edition

Participation Research Cluster, Institute of Development Studies. [Translating face-to-face participatory workshops to an online setting](#)

PRIA International Academy (2014) [Participatory Training Methodology](#). (PDF)

University of Calgary (2021). Courageous Conversations: [Decolonization, Disciplines, and Indigenous Knowledges in the University](#). With Dr. Catherine Odora Hoppers. (Video)

Zalat MM, Hamed MS, Bolbol SA (2021) [The experiences, challenges, and acceptance of e-learning as a tool for teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic among university medical staff](#). PLoS ONE 16(3): e0248758.

Tools & Services

Selected digital tools, platforms and services with a focus on community-driven and preprint-based peer review

- PREreview, prereview.org
- Hypothes.is, web.hypothes.is/research
- Science Open peer review, about.scienceopen.com/peer-review-guidelines
- Qeios peer review, qeios.com/discover?type=review
- Peer Community In, peercommunityin.org
- Society, sciety.org

ABOUT OPEN PEER REVIEWERS IN AFRICA

Open Peer Reviewers in Africa⁷ is a Wellcome-funded project developed as a collaboration between 5 organizations AfricArXiv, Eider Africa, eLife, PRereview, and the Training Centre in Communication (TCC Africa) Africa. Our work focused on developing content and a Train-of-Trainer model for a new peer review training program for early to mid-career researchers based in Africa. The course aims to foster the participation of African researchers in peer review and build capacity around, especially the open review of preprints. Learn more about the partner organizations below.

AfricArXiv is a community-led digital archive for African research, working towards building an African-owned open scholarly repository; a knowledge commons of African scholarly works to catalyze the African Renaissance. We partner with established scholarly repository services to provide a platform for African scientists of any discipline to present their research findings and connect with other researchers on the African continent and globally. Find out more about AfricArXiv at info.africarxiv.org.

Eider Africa is an organization that conducts research, co-designs and implements collaboratively, offline and online research mentorship programs for scholars in Africa. We train mentors to start their mentorship programs. We believe in peer-to-peer learning, learning research by practice, caring for the whole researcher and lifelong learning. We have grown a vibrant community of researchers in our research journal clubs and work with university lecturers to develop transformative inclusive research training. Learn more at eiderafricaltd.org.

eLife is a non-profit organization created by funders and led by researchers. Our mission is to accelerate discovery by operating a platform for research communication that encourages and recognises the most responsible behaviors. We seek to promote a research culture that supports collaboration, diversity and inclusion, and openness, and we support preprints and open-science practices. eLife receives financial support and strategic guidance from the [Howard Hughes Medical Institute](http://www.hughesmedical.org), the [Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation](http://www.knutandalicewallenberg.org), the [Max Planck Society](http://www.mpsociety.org) and [Wellcome](http://www.wellcome.org). Learn more at elifesciences.org/about.

PRereview is an open project fiscally sponsored by the non-profit organization [Code for Science and Society](http://codeforscience.org). Our mission is to bring more equity and transparency to the scholarly

⁷elifesciences.org/for-the-press/ce2d4a3e/elife-prereview-and-partners-develop-course-to-involve-more-african-researchers-in-peer-review

peer-review process. We design and develop open-source infrastructure to enable constructive feedback to preprints, we run peer review mentoring and training programs, and we partner with like-minded organizations to organize events that provide opportunities for researchers to create meaningful collaborations and connections, defeating cultural and geographical barriers. Learn more about PREreview at prereview.org.

Training Centre in Communication (TCC Africa) is the first African-based training centre to teach effective communication skills to scientists. TCC Africa is an award-winning Trust, established as a non-profit entity in 2006 and is registered in Kenya. TCC Africa provides capacity support in improving researchers' output and visibility through training in scholarly and science communication. Find out more about TCC Africa at tcc-africa.org.

CONTACT INFORMATION AND FEEDBACK

If you have any questions or would like to provide feedback to this guide, please email contact@prereview.org or community@elifesciences.org. Thank you!